

Analysis of CMC of polyoxyethylene(20)sorbitan monopalmitate (Tween-40) and cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide (CTAB) in aqueous medium

T. B. Sinha^{a,b}, H. S. Das^b, R. K. Dubey^b, R. Das^b, G. Roymahapatra^b and P. K. Khatua^{*a,b}

^aICARE School of Research & Development, University of Mysore, ICARE Complex, Haldia-721 657, West Bengal, India

^bDepartment of Applied Science, Haldia Institute of Technology, Haldia-721 657, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pijuskhatua@gmail.com

Manuscript received 01 November 2017, accepted 24 November 2017

Abstract : In aqueous environment of different concentration ratio of CTAB and Tween-40 formed mixed micelles. In this present paper the mixed micelles and their critical micellar concentration (CMC) has been studied by different instrumental techniques like spectrophotometric, spectrofluorometric by using a probe 1-anilinonaphthalene-8-sulfonic acid (1,8-ANS) as well as conductometric, potentiometric by using Clint, Motomura, Rosen, Rubingh, Blankschtein *et al.*, and Rubingh and Holland equation for verification of the experimental CMC, composition parameters, quantification of interaction among the mixed micelle components, and estimation of their activity coefficients.

Keywords : Mixed micelles, CTAB, Tween-40, 1,8-ANS, CMC.

Introduction

In the field of chemistry, bio-chemistry, drug industry, biotechnology, pharmaceuticals engineering etc. micellar environment have wide range of application. From the modern study¹⁻³ it has been implied that micellar environments are more active and have more potential on the view points of fundamental, technological, pharmaceutical, bio-chemical consideration. To prepare a mixed micelle, more than one surfactant is necessary in the form of any one mode i.e. ionic-ionic and ionic-nonionic, nonionic-nonionic⁴⁻⁹. More than one surface active agent when mixed in definite proportion form mixed micelles which are widely used in industrial preparation as well as pharmaceuticals and medical applications.

In mixed surfactant environment with increase in concentration of surfactant system they aggregate and formed micelle at a particular concentration called CMC. The formation of CMC does not only concentration depended; it also depends other factors like temperature, additives, pressure and pH of the environment. Mixed micelles have some special charac-

teristics¹⁰⁻¹⁷ than the individual micelle formed only from one surfactant. So the characterization of CMC for mixed surfactant is very much important in the field of medicine, pharmaceuticals, dyeing cloths etc.

The present study is associated with two surfactants Tween-40 and CTAB. The physical and chemical properties of both surfactants are very much dependent on their different concentration ratio. We have studied CMC and other properties like thermodynamics of micellization and interfacial adsorption, polarity, composition and interaction, counter ion binding of the mixed micellar system, have been determined by using the theory of Clint¹⁸, Motomura¹⁹, Rubingh²⁰ and Blankschtein^{21,22} to better understand the behavior of binary combination of surfactants having different characteristics.

Experimental

The dye 1,8-ANS was crystallized thrice from an ethanol-water mixture^{23,24}. The amphiphiles, polyoxyethylene(20)sorbitan monopalmitate (Tween-40) and CTAB were of E. Merck (Germany) prod-

ucts. They were used as received without further purification as their impurities were checked by emission measurements and found absent. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. All measurements were taken in a thermostat at 298 ± 0.1 K.

Methods :

Surface tension :

Surface tension of surfactants in aqueous medium at different concentrations was measured by using a du Noüy tensiometer (Krüss, Germany) using a platinum ring by the technique of surface-ring detachment. The experimental technique of measurements can be found elsewhere¹⁰⁻¹⁴. In an experimental run, concentrated surfactant solution was added to water in the glass vessel with the help of a Hamilton micro syringe progressively at constant temperature and then surface tension was measured after proper and thorough mixing and equilibration. Each experiment was repeated thrice to get consistent and reproducible results. The results were accurate within ± 0.1 dyne cm^{-1} .

Conductometry :

The conductometric measurements were taken with a Jenway (UK) conductometer using a conductometric cell of cell constant 1.00 cm^{-1} . Accuracy of the measured conductance was within $\pm 0.5\%$. The detailed measurements were presented earlier¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

Spectrophotometry :

Absorption spectra were recorded using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Lambda-35 (USA), Perkin-Elmer) with matched pair of silica cuvettes (path lengths 1 cm). Each and every fluorescence measurements were carried out in a thermostat where maximum temperature varies within $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and mean values were taken for data analysis.

Fluorometry :

Fluorescence spectra were measured using a spectrofluorimeter LS-55 (USA, Perkin-Elmer) with a slit width 2.5 nm. The excitation and emission wavelengths were 350 nm and 550 nm respectively. The concentration of 1,8-ANS used was of the order of $10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. All spectral measurements were duplicated in a constant temperature water bath where

accuracy is within $\pm 0.5\%$. Measurements of fluorescence decay were done using time linked single photon plus technique with light source of nanosecond diode laser at 370 nm (IBH, nanoled-7) having a typical response time of 1.1 ns. We used IBHDAS-6 decay analysis software to get computational results. The whole experiments were done at temperature 25°C .

Life-time measurement :

Life-time of 1,8-ANS in the mixed micellar system of Tween-40 and CTAB (at different molar ratio) was measured with a picosecond single photon counting spectrofluorometer. For this study, the sample solutions were excited at 450 nm of a picosecond light emitting laser diode of pulse duration 200 ps in a spectrofluorometer of Fluorocube model (IBH, UK). The fluorescence was detected at magic angle polarization. The detector was a Hamamatsu MCP photomultiplier (2809U). The time resolution of the setup was ≈ 100 ps. The solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling with purified N_2 gas for 30 min at 298 K. All decay curves were single exponential.

Results and discussion

Critical micelle concentration :

The different proportions of CTAB and Tween-40 in the molar ratio of 1 : 3, 1 : 2, 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 were used to find CMC values by using different instrumental methods as discussed above. From the plot of surface tension (γ) vs log [surfactant] as shown in Fig. 1, the CMC values were determined and given in Table 1.

The CMC values of the different combinations of two surfactants were also determined from the plot of conductance vs [surfactant] as shown in Fig. 2 and given in Table 1. The dye molecule, 1,8-ANS has been used as probe for the characterization of the surfactant mixture by absorbance and fluorescence method. The absorbance and fluorescence intensity of 1,8-ANS increases with [surfactant]. The ratio of the absorbance (or fluorescence) in the presence of surfactant, A (or F) to that in the absence of surfactant, A_0 or F_0 at the maximum absorbance or fluorescence when plotted against log (surfactant) as shown

Fig. 1. Plot of surface tension (γ) vs log [mix. sur.]; (a) (O-O), (b) (∇ - ∇), (c) (Δ - Δ), (d) (\square - \square), (e) (\blacksquare - \blacksquare) represent 3 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 molar ratio of CTAB and Tween-40 mixture respectively.

in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, show a breaks in the linear plot. Breaking point indicates CMC values, given in Table 1. From conductance and tensiometric measurements also a break has been obtained. The average values of CMC vary in low range of change in concentration of CTAB and Tween-40 surfactant mixture obtained by different methods.

Adsorption at air/water interface :

The orientation of the surfactants at air/water interface decreases surface tension of the medium. The interfacial adsorption per unit area of surface at various concentrations can be calculated using Gibbs

Fig. 2. Plot of conductance (mho) vs $-\log$ [mix. sur.]; (a) (O-O), (b) (Δ - Δ), (c) (∇ - ∇), (d) (\square - \square), (e) (+-+) represent 3 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 molar ratio of CTAB and Tween-40 mixture respectively.

adsorption equation. The detailed explanation of this equation has already been reported earlier¹²⁻¹⁴. The total surface excess at the air/water interface is obtained from the following relation,

$$\Gamma_{\max} = \frac{1}{2.303RT} \lim_{C \rightarrow \text{CMC}} \frac{d\pi}{d \log C} \quad (1)$$

where, π is the surface pressure (surface tension of water minus the surface tension of the surfactant so-

Table 1. Critical micellar concentration^a (CMC) of binary combinations of CTAB and Tween-40 at 298 K

Mole fraction (α) of CTAB, (α_{CTAB})	CMC $\times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)					According to Clint's equation
	Tens.	Cond.	Abs.	Fluo.	Av.	
0	0.231	-	0.212	0.202	0.215	-
0.25	0.417	0.421	0.421	0.418	0.419	0.288
0.33	0.455	0.469	0.464	0.457	0.461	0.318
0.50	0.549	0.542	0.538	0.534	0.541	0.416
0.67	0.631	0.628	0.632	0.628	0.629	0.622
0.75	0.812	0.809	0.818	0.801	0.812	0.809
1.00 ^b	8.501	8.521	8.592	8.418	8.508	-

^aValues in parentheses indicate CMC at higher region, ^bRef. 13.

Fig. 3. Plot of ratio of absorbances (A/A_0) vs $-\log$ [mix. sur.]; (a) (\blacklozenge), (b) (\triangle), (c) (∇), (d) (\square), (e) (\circ) represent 3 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 molar ratio of CTAB and Tween-40 mixture respectively.

Fig. 4. Plot of ratio of fluorescence intensity (F/F_0) vs $-\log$ [mix. sur.]; (a) (∇), (b) (\diamond), (c) (\square), (d) (\triangle), (e) (\circ) represent 3 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 molar ratio of CTAB and Tween-40 mixture respectively.

lution) and C is the surfactant concentration in mol dm^{-3} . The minimum area per adsorbed molecule (A_{\min}) has been calculated by the equation,

$$A_{\min} = 10^{18} / N\Gamma_{\max} \quad (2)$$

where, N is the Avogadro's number, the values of $(d\pi/d \log C)$ have been obtained from the least-square slopes of the π vs $\log C$ plot which has not been shown to save space. The π_{CMC} , Γ_{\max} and A_{\min} values for the surfactant mixture are presented in Table 2. The values of Γ_{\max} increase with increase in mole fraction of CTAB in the mixture indicating the increase of synergetic interaction among the adsorbed CTAB in the layers of the micelles. A_{\min} values of the mixtures follow the reverse order. For the system, the observed Γ_{\max} values are close to the calculated values.

Thermodynamics of micellization and interfacial adsorption :

The standard free energy of micellization per mole

of monomer unit (ΔG_m^0) for the binary combinations was evaluated from the relation,

$$\Delta G_m^0 = (1+g)RT \ln X_{\text{CMC}}$$

where, g is the fraction of counter ions bound to the micelle determined conductometrically¹⁵ and X_{CMC} is the CMC expressed in mole fraction unit. The standard state was the hypothetical state of unit mole fraction. The standard enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m^0) was determined calorimetrically, and the standard entropy of micellization (ΔS_m^0) was calculated applying the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation,

$$\Delta G_m^0 = \Delta H_m^0 - T\Delta S_m^0$$

for the micellization of binary surfactant mixtures.

Counter ion binding :

The fraction of the counter ions bound to the micelle has been evaluated conductometrically from the ratio of the post micellar and pre micellar slopes of the plot of conductance vs concentration of the surfactant solution. This fraction of the counter ion binding

Table 2. Thermodynamic and micellization behaviors of binary mixtures of CTAB and Tween-40 at 298 K

α_{CTAB}	m/n	$10^6 \Gamma_{\text{max}}$ (mol m ⁻²)	A_{min} (nm ²)	π_{CMC} (erg cm ⁻²)	$-\Delta G_{\text{m}}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_{m}^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H_{\text{m}}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G_{\text{m}}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
0.00	–	1.19	1.33	27.19	26.68	89.56	8.33	48.63
0.25	0.11	2.15	0.79	25.49	27.59	92.62	1.78	39.40
0.33	0.12	2.19	0.74	20.02	27.67	93.02	1.07	36.71
0.50	0.19	2.02	0.9	19.06	29.00	97.33	1.29	38.55
0.67	0.22	2.55	0.66	18.44	29.19	97.98	2.37	36.40
0.75	0.41	2.29	0.72	17.88	32.78	110.02	1.53	40.58
1.00	0.58	2.33	0.69	31.99	28.18	94.59	6.91	41.87

The average errors in each of the ΔG_{m}^0 , ΔS_{m}^0 and ΔG_{ad}^0 are $\pm 3\%$.

is represented by ‘ m/n ’, where ‘ m ’ is the number of the counter ions bound per micelle and ‘ n ’ is the aggregation number. With increase in concentration of CTAB in the mixture, the value of counter ion binding increases. This may be due to two factors, (i) with increase in concentration of CTAB the number of counter ions in the double layer increases and (ii) decrease in CMC is paralleled by the increase in aggregation number. Hence with decrease in concentration of CTAB in the system, counter ion binding decreases. The CMC of the binary combinations increases with increasing proportion of CTAB in the mixture. The binary mixtures of CTAB with other cationic surfactant have shown two break points, which have been reported as two CMC values^{25–26}. Table 1 shows that CMC values were also obtained for binary mixture of CTAB with nonionic surfactant Tween-40. The CMC values obtained from different techniques are different and this difference may be due to the method of measurement.

Adsorption energetics of micellization and interfacial adsorption :

The standard free energy of micellization per mole of monomer unit (ΔG_{m}^0) for the CTAB and Tween-40 mixture was evaluated by applying the equation,

$$\Delta G_{\text{m}}^0 = \left(1 + \frac{m}{n}\right) RT \ln \text{CMC} \quad (3)$$

where, ‘ m/n ’ is the fraction of counter ions bound to the micelle. The standard free energy of interfacial adsorption (ΔG_{ad}^0) at the air/saturated monolayer interface has been obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0 = \Delta G_{\text{m}}^0 - \left(\frac{\pi_{\text{CMC}}}{\Gamma_{\text{max}}}\right) \quad (4)$$

where, π_{CMC} is the surface pressure at CMC. The entropy of micellization, ΔS_{m}^0 is obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta G_{\text{m}}^0 = -T\Delta S_{\text{m}}^0 \quad (5)$$

neglecting the enthalpy of micellization, which could not be measured in a micro calorimeter (Omega, ITC, USA).

The ΔH_{m}^0 values of similar system with CMC of the order 10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ are observed to be extremely low and negligible. The counter ion binding for the mixed surfactants increases with increasing mole fraction of CTAB. The values of ΔG_{m}^0 in Table 2 show that the binary combinations are equally spontaneous. The standard free energy of interfacial adsorption (ΔG_{ad}^0) follows the same trend as ΔG_{m}^0 . The entropy values are fairly large and positive indicating the micellization process is entropy controlled.

Solvent parameters :

The solvent parameters, dielectric constant etc. can be correlated with the Stokes shift (the shift between the absorbance and emission) of the dye (1,8-ANS) in mixed micellar medium. The spectral shift observed can be used as a guide to the interaction of the dye with mixed micelles.

The spectral shift $\Delta\bar{\nu} = (\bar{\nu}_{\text{a}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{f}})$, where $\bar{\nu}_{\text{a}}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{f}}$ refer to the frequencies of absorbance and fluorescence respectively for 1,8-ANS in mixed micelles are presented in Table 3. The relation $\Delta\bar{\nu}$ of 1,8-ANS in

Table 3. Stokes, shift, life-time dielectric constant, values and $E_T(30)$ and orientation polarizability values of the surfactant mixtures

α_{CTAB}	Lifetime (ns)	$\Delta\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1})	D	Orientation polarizability	$E_T(30)$ (kcal mol^{-1})
0.25	2.77	6191	36.7	0.283	43.9
0.33	2.69	6921	37.4	0.305	46
0.50	2.61	7245	24.6	0.289	51.9
0.67	2.56	7421	32.70	0.308	55.5
0.75	2.45	7492	40.7	0.273	56.3

mixed micelles are correlated with the dielectric constant, $E_T(30)$ and orientation polarizability (Δf) by comparing $\Delta\bar{\nu}$ of 1,8-ANS with the dielectric constant (D), $E_T(30)$ and orientation polarizability (Δf)^{27,28} in various protic and aprotic solvent systems. However the $\Delta\bar{\nu}$ values of different solvents do not exhibit a direct correlation with the dielectric constant, D and orientation polarizability but varies linearly with $E_T(30)$ values for the present mixed micellar media have been found using the measured $\Delta\bar{\nu}$ values from the Fig. 5. and Fig. 6. Here an indirect method has been adopted for the evaluation of D , Δf and $E_T(30)$ in mixed micellar system. The D , Δf and $E_T(30)$ values obtained from different solvent have been used to estimate the corresponding D values from the linear plot between D and Δf and $E_T(30)$ for the mixed micellar system. The D values are presented in

Fig. 5. Plot of Stokes' shift vs $E_T(30)$ parameter of 1,8-ANS in different solvents environment.

Fig. 6. Solvent induced Stokes' shift of 1,8-ANS vs solvent orientation polarizability in different solvents environment.

Table 3. The values of dielectric constant for the mixed micellar system denote the micellar polarity, which is responsible for the solubilisation of the additive in a micelle and for the function and dissociation of the probe molecule in the micellar region. The $E_T(30)$ values increase with decreasing concentration of CTAB in the mixture. This needs further study in future.

Mixed micellar composition and interaction :

The mixture of surfactants can form mixed micelles, which are of both types, ideal and nonideal. The CMC can be evaluated by using the ideal equation of Clint¹⁸ for dilute solution (neglecting the activity coefficient of the solution),

$$\frac{1}{\text{CMC}_{\text{mix}}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_i}{\text{CMC}_i} \quad (6)$$

where, CMC_{mix} and CMC_i are the critical micellar concentrations of the mixture and the i -th component respectively and α_i is the mole fraction of i -th component in solution. From the equation⁶, the calculated CMC values are presented in Table 1. The experimental CMC in the lower region of concentration is higher than the calculated CMC for the mixtures indicating the presence of non-ideality due to mutual interaction of the surfactants in the micelle.

The theoretical treatments of Motomura¹⁹, Rubingh²⁰, Sarmoria²¹, Puvvada and Blankschtein (SPB)^{21,22} provide methods to estimate the composition and micellar interaction in the mixed micelles as well as predicting CMC and f_i . According to Motomura's thermodynamic treatment¹⁹ for the system of the mixed micelles, micellization is considered like a macroscopic bulk phase and energetic parameters associated with the progress are given by the excess thermodynamic quantities. In Table 4, X_M represents the mole fraction of a surfactant in the mixed micelle. The values of X_M are positive for all mole fractions of CTAB except $\alpha_{CTAB} = 0.75$ which is negative. The negative value of X_M is reported elsewhere¹¹.

The regular solution theory for the mixed micelles was given by Rubingh²⁰. According to this theory, micellar mole fraction (X_R), interaction parameter (β_R) and activity coefficients (f_R) of binary combinations have been calculated following relevant equations and procedures¹⁴. The results are presented in Table 4. The micellar mole fraction (X_R) is very low for higher mole fraction of CTAB. The amphiphilic mutual interaction parameter (β_R) values are marginally positive indicating minor synergism. Similar results have been obtained with other surfactant mixtures¹¹. The

activity coefficients of CTAB, f_R^{CTAB} in mixed micelles are unusual whereas those for Tw-40, f_R^{Tw} are unity. This manifests molecular activity phenomenon of a pair of amphiphiles having dissimilar head and tail groups.

Blankschtein suggested a molecular thermodynamic theory to mixtures of surfactants to predict the CMC, micellar shape and size between the binary components²¹. The modified Blankschtein equation is,

$$\frac{1}{CMC_{mix}} = \frac{\alpha}{f_{SPB}^1 CMC_1} + \frac{1-\alpha}{f_{SPB}^2 CMC_2} \quad (7)$$

where, the terms f_{SPB}^1 and f_{SPB}^2 are the activity coefficients of surfactants 1 and 2 in the mixed micelle. The activity coefficients are given as,

$$f_{SPB}^1 = \exp \left[\frac{\beta_{12}(1-\alpha^*)^2}{kT} \right] \quad (8)$$

and

$$f_{SPB}^2 = \exp \left[\frac{\beta_{12}(\alpha^*)^2}{kT} \right] \quad (9)$$

where, α^* is the optimal micellar composition, β_{12} is the predicted interaction parameter between the surfactants 1 and 2, k is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the absolute temperature. The relation to evaluate β_{12} for the estimation of activity coefficients is,

$$\frac{\beta_{12}(1-2\alpha^*)}{kT} + \ln \left(\frac{\alpha^*}{1-\alpha^*} \right) = \ln \left[\frac{(\alpha) CMC_2}{(1-\alpha) CMC_1} \right] \quad (10)$$

From Table 4, it is observed that X_{SPB} (or α^*) increases with increasing α_{CTAB} and X_{SPB} deviates more from the values of X_M and X_R . The interaction pa-

Table 4. Micellar compositions ($X_M/X_R/X_{SPB}$), interaction parameters [β_R/β_{SPB} (kT)], activity coefficients (f_R/f_{SPB}), and CMC's of CTAB and Tween-40 at 298 K by different theoretical methods at different compositions (α)

α_{CTAB}	$X_M/X_R/X_{SPB}$	β_R/β_{SPB} (kT)	$f_R^{CTAB}/f_{SPB}^{CTAB}$	f_R^{Tw}/f_{SPB}^{Tw}	CMC $\times 10^4$ /mol dm ⁻³ Obs./SPB/Clint
0.25	0.12/ - /0.21	- /-4.54	- /0.059	- /0.819	0.419/0.21/0.290
0.33	0.05/ - /0.23	- /-4.31	- /0.036	- /0.796	0.461/0.20/0.320
0.50	0.29/ - /0.27	- /-4.02	- /0.117	- /0.746	0.541/0.27/0.420
0.67	0.47/0.01/0.31	1.63/-3.85	4.89/0.160	1.00/0.691	0.629/0.36/0.620
0.75	-0.16/0.04/0.34	0.72/-3.58	1.94/0.210	1.0/0.661	0.812/0.45/0.810

parameter, β_{SPB} decreases with increasing mole fraction of CTAB. The negative values of β_{SPB} indicate the attractive interactions between the surfactants. The activity coefficient values of CTAB, $f_{\text{SPB}}^{\text{CTAB}}$ are low compared to $f_{\text{SPB}}^{\text{Tw}}$. The activity coefficients of non-ionic amphiphile, Tween-40 for both Rubingh and SPB methods (f_{R}^{Tw} and $f_{\text{SPB}}^{\text{Tw}}$) are nearly unity. The CMC values evaluated by the SPB method are much lower than those obtained experimentally and those calculated by Clint's method. There are deviations indicating the presence of non-ideality due to mutual interaction of surfactants in the micelle.

Life time measurement :

Fluorescence life time plays an important guide to explain local environment where the fluorophore is reside and provides exceptional insights into the systems under analysis. In our present study, fluorescence decay behaviour of the probe has also been

Fig. 7. Fluorescence decay of 1,8-ANS in mixed micellar solution of CTAB and Tween-40 at different ratio, $[1,8\text{-ANS}] = 0.467 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

explored as a function of change in concentration of surfactants. The fluorescence decay behaviour is found to be mono-exponential in nature as shown in Fig. 7. The life time values are given in Table 3. The probe life time decrease with increase in concentration and polarity of CTAB indicate intermolecular hydrogen

bonding takes place between S_1 state the dye molecule and CTAB molecules direct to an increase in the non radiative relaxation rates from S_1 to S_0 consequently life time decrease.

Conclusions

The binary combinations of CTAB-Tween-40 have the CMC values slightly higher than those calculated by the Clint's¹⁸ equation indicating the presence of non-ideality. The values of counter ion binding are low. The values of dielectric constant for this mixed micellar system vary inversely with concentration of CTAB in the mixture, which needs further investigation.

This work also presents a theoretical interpretation of the mixed micelle. The mole fractional concentration of the component in the micelle is not equal to the stoichiometric composition; the extent of transfer of CTAB from solution into the micelles is very low. The mixture shows minor attractive interaction ($-ve \beta_{\text{SPB}}$) due to structural differences between tail and head groups of CTAB and Tween-40 and thus the mixtures have heterogeneous character.

Acknowledgement

Authors acknowledge Department of Science and Technology, Government of India [DST/TM/SERI/2K10/67(G)] for financial support for pursuing the R & D activity.

References

1. Z. Zhang and C. Yan Lin, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2000, **130**, 139.
2. M. Almgren and A. Valstar, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 2635.
3. D. Attwood and A. T. Florence, "Surfactant Systems", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1983, 116.
4. R. M. Hill, in "Mixed Surfactant System", eds. K. Ogino and M. Abe, Surfactant Science Series 46, Dekker, New York, 1993, Chap. II.
5. P. M. Holland and D. N. Rubingh, in "Mixed Surfactant System", eds. P. M. Holland and D. N. Rubingh, ACS Symposium Series 501, P. I. Am. Chem. Soc., Washington, DC, 1992.
6. J. H. Clint, "Surfactant Aggregation", Blackie, Chapman and Hall, New York, 1992.
7. P. C. Griffiths, M. L. Wharton, R. J. Abbott, W. Kwan, A. R. Pitt, A. M. Howe, S. M. King and R. K. Heenan,

Sinha *et al.* : Analysis of CMC of polyoxyethylene(20)sorbitan monopalmitate *etc.*

- J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1999, **215**, 114.
8. S. Ghosh and S. P. Moulik, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1999, **38A**, 10.
 9. M. E. Haque, A. R. Das and S. P. Moulik, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1999, **217**, 1.
 10. S. Ghosh and S. P. Moulik, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1998, **208**, 357.
 11. S. P. Moulik and S. Ghosh, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 1997, **72**, 145.
 12. D. K. Chattoraj and R. P. Pal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 410.
 13. S. P. Moulik, M. E. Haque, P. K. Jana and A. R. Das, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 701.
 14. S. Ghosh, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2001, **244**, 128.
 15. A. D. Burman, T. Dey, B. Mukherjee and A. R. Das, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 10020.
 16. S. R. Raghavan, G. Fritz and E. W. Kaler, *Langmuir*, 2002, **18**, 3797.
 17. H. P. Moises de Oliveira and M. H. Gehlen, *Langmuir*, 2002, **18**, 3792.
 18. J. H. Clint, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1975, **71**, 1327.
 19. (a) K. Motomura, M. Yamanaka and M. Aratono, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1984, **262**, 948; (b) K. Motomura, M. Aratono, K. Ogino and M. Abe, in "Mixed Surfactant Systems", eds. K. Ogino and M. Abe, Dekker, New York, 1993, 99.
 20. D. N. Rubingh, in "Solution Chemistry of Surfactants", ed. K. L. Mittal, Plenum, New York, 1979, Vol. 1, 337.
 21. (a) C. Sarmoria, S. Puvvada and D. Blankschtein, *Langmuir*, 1992, **8**, 2690; (b) S. Puvvada and D. Blankschtein, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 5567; (c) S. Puvvada and D. Blankschtein, in "Mixed Surfactant Systems", eds. P. M. Holland and D. N. Rubingh, ACS Symposium Series 501, Am. Chem. Soc., Washington, DC, 1992, 96.
 22. A. Shiloach and D. Blankschtein, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 1618.
 23. S. C. Bhattacharya, H. Das and S. P. Moulik, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1994, **79**, 109.
 24. S. C. Bhattacharya, P. Roy and S. P. Moulik, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1995, **88**, 139.
 25. R. Bury, C. Treimer, C. Chevalet and A. Makayssi, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1991, **251**, 69.
 26. C. Treiner and A. Makayssi, *Langmuir*, 1992, **8**, 794.
 27. A. Sarkar, P. Banerjee, S. Hossain, S. Bhattacharya and S. C. Bhattacharya, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2009, **27**, 1097.
 28. D. Patra and C. Barkat, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2011, **79**, 1034.

